

VERSION v7

Standard Operating Procedure

537DSSD - DRUG INTERACTION

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Seventh Draft

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The CEO is a Member of PIUG, IEEE, AUTM & LES

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1. Purpose

The purpose of this document is to provide instructions for the manual annotation using AnnotationPress tool. The purpose of the project is to extract Pharmacokinetic data from the given set of publications. The following major Pharmacokinetic information should be extracted:

- **Claim**
- **Object drug, dose, form, and schedule**
- **Precipitant drug, dose, form, and schedule**
- **AUC Ratio**
- **C_{max} Ratio**
- **Clearance Ratio**
- **Half-life (T_{1/2}) Ratio**
- **[Number of] Participants**
- **Evidence Relationship**
- **Randomization**

2. Scope

The scope of this pharmacokinetic data curation project is to identify the drug interaction data and its effects. There will be two types of drugs discussed in most of the cases; these are Object Drug and Precipitant Drug.

3. Source

- ✓ List of publications provided to E-Merge tech by University of Pittsburgh.

4. Definitions

- **Claim:** An assertion about a relationship between entities in the domain of discourse (in this case drug-drug interactions) that is supported or refuted by evidence. The word claim in this

context is a generally synonymous with assertion though the latter is used more often to describe a claim's logical formalization.

- **Object Drug:** The drug whose action is altered by the interaction
- **Precipitant Drug:** The drug that causes the altered action of the altered drug
- **AUC:** (Definite Integral) is the plot of concentration of drug in blood plasma against time. Usually it is calculated from the start of the administration of the drug till the drug concentration becomes negligible
- **AUC Ratio:** The ratio of the AUC (as fold or percent increase or decrease) of the object drug in the presence of the purported precipitant drug
- **C_{max}:** It is defined as maximum (or peak) serum concentration that a drug achieves in a specified compartment or test area of the body after the drug has been administered and prior to the administration of a second dose
- **C_{max} Ratio:** The ratio of the C_{max} (as fold or percent increase or decrease) of the object drug in the presence of the purported precipitant drug
- **T_{1/2}:** (Half life) The duration of action of the drug is known as Half-life. This is the time period required by the drug to reach its concentration or amount to half
- **T_{1/2} Ratio:** The ratio of the T_{1/2} (as fold or percent increase or decrease) of the object drug in the presence of the purported precipitant drug
- **Clearance:** The rate at which a drug is removed from the plasma is known as clearance
- **Clearance Ratio:** The ratio of the Clearance (as fold or percent increase or decrease) of the object drug in the presence of the purported precipitant drug
- **Number of participants:** The number of participants entered into a clinical trial. (Note: this is different than number of participants who complete, which is participants - dropouts)
- **Evidence Relationship:** If the evidence supports or refutes the claim.

- **Randomization:** 'Yes' if the study randomized participants to exposure or order of exposure

5. Work Flow

6. General Instructions

E-Merge tech will be provided with an input spreadsheet and access to an online annotation interface:

1. **Set Up Annotation Tool:** The web interface used for annotation

(1) Install VPN client and remote into our network.

- Install VPN client (Pulse Secure) on your computer
- Open up Pulse Secure and add a connection like below

- Click Connect to continue and select Network Connect to continue

- Type in the username “ANNOTAT1” and password to connect

- Select VPN role “Firewall-DBMI-annotator-SecureConnect” and click connect

Note: We'll have 5 accounts for you later to do annotations. The current one is just for testing.

(2) Install remote desktop

- Download NoMachine as the remote desktop tool from <https://www.nomachine.com>

- Open up NoMachine to create a new connection after installation. Here are the connection information: **Protocol: NX**

Host IP: 10.247.2.23, Port: 4000

Authentication method: password

Proxy: Don't use a proxy

- After you click continue, please click yes if there is any warning box pops up. Then, type in username “annotat1” and password to log in VLAN server

- After you log in to the server, you will see this screen. The content in this screen depends.
Note: Please DON'T click *Physical Display*.

- If your account name (e.g. annotat1) already exists in above screen, please click and connect it. If your account name doesn't exist, please click *Create a new desktop* and choose *Create a new virtual desktop*. **Note:** Please DON'T create a new desktop when there are already four virtual desktops. In this situation, please log in with another account or contact us (yin2@pitt.edu, wez61@pitt.edu).

- Please log out after you finished your task. Right click on the Desktop. Click the *Applications* in the list, and then choose *Log Out* option.

- Open Browser. Please right click on the Desktop. Click the *Applications* in the list, and then choose *Web Browser* option. A Firefox browser will pop up.

- Then you can type in the url <http://localhost/dbmiannotator> to access our annotator tool. If you see an interface like this on the screen, congratulation, you access the annotation tool successfully.

- (3) After you see the login page, click login button and type in the username "test@gmail.com" and password to start the work.
 - (4) The next step is to open up the input file, find the articles are assigned and annotate their information using the annotation tool.
2. **Open Up Input File:** The file lists all the articles and information are needed for doing annotations. This file (*wiley-articles-to-screen.xls*) is on the desktop. Please open it with the *Gnumeric*.

Process

(1) In this spreadsheet, please take the annotation notes in the column *Annotation completed?* and column *Annotator Notes?*

L	M	N	O
The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the methods	The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the results	Annotation completed?	Annotator Notes?
Page 313-318	Table 1, Figure 1		
p927-930 p927-930	Table 1, 2 Figure 2 in text only		
two randomized crossover studies were conducted.	Fig 4, Table , fig 5		

(2) In the annotation interface, find the article needs to be annotated and open its article link listed in input column *Article Link*

For example: Article (Laugesen_2005_15903129),
Article Link (<http://localhost/wiley/wiley15903129.html>)

A	B	C	D	E
No.	Article Link	Article	Study Type	This is evidence
11	http://localhost/wiley/wiley15903129.html	Laugesen_2005_15903129	Clinical study	For
12	http://localhost/wiley/wiley15966919.html	Mattichak_2005_15966919	n/a	
13	http://localhost/wiley/wiley16027403.html	Simonson_2005_16027403	Clinical study	Against
14	http://localhost/wiley/wiley16027403.html	Simonson_2005_16027403	Clinical study	Against
15	http://localhost/wiley/wiley16027406.html	Gustavson_2005_16027406	n/a	For
16	http://localhost/wiley/wiley16084850.html	Backman_2005_16084850	Clinical study	For

Note: the table below explains all the information is needed by annotation tool and the columns in the input file.

Information is needed by annotation tool	Information location in input file
--	------------------------------------

Article to be annotated	<i>Column: Article</i>
Main Claim	<i>Column: The sentence(s) that state the main assertion</i>
Drug1	<i>Column: Drug</i>
Relationship	<i>Column: Property</i>
Method type	<i>Column: Study Type</i>
Drug2/inhibitor	<i>Column: Value (drop down - for non-quantitative</i>
Rejected Evidence	<i>Column: Meets inclusion criteria? and Column: If you entered 'No' - explain why</i>
Participants	<i>Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the methods and Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the results</i>
AUC Ratio, Cmax Ratio, Clearance Ratio, and/or Half-life (T1/2) Ratio	<i>Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the results</i>
Ev_relationship (evidence relationship)	<i>Column: This is evidence. If it's an "against", then selects "refuse", otherwise selects "support".</i>

(3) In the annotation interface, find the article needs to be annotated and open its article link listed in input column *Article Link*

Comparative Pharmacokinetic Interaction Profiles of Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin When Coadministered With Cytochrome P450 Inhibitors

Terry A. Jacobson, MD

Three hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme-A reductase inhibitors (statins) are first-line treatments for hypercholesterolemia. Although serologically well tolerated, treatment with statins carries a small risk of myopathy or potentially fatal rhabdomyolysis, particularly when coadministered with medications that increase their systemic exposure. Studies compared the multiple-dose pharmacokinetic interaction profiles of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin when coadministered with 4 inhibitors of cytochrome P450-3A4 isoenzymes in healthy subjects. Compared with pravastatin alone, coadministration of verapamil, nifedipine, or itraconazole with pravastatin was associated with no significant changes in pravastatin pharmacokinetics. However, concomitant verapamil increased the simvastatin area under the concentration-time curve (AUC) approximately fourfold, the maximum serum concentration (C_{max}) fivefold, and the active metabolite simvastatin acid AUC and C_{max} approximately four- and threefold, respectively (all comparisons p < 0.001). Similar (greater than fourfold) important increases in these parameters and a >60% increase in the serum half-life (p = 0.03) of atorvastatin were observed when coadministered with nifedipine. The half-life of atorvastatin also increased by ~60% (p = 0.052) when coadministered with itraconazole, which elicited a 2.4-fold increase in the C_{max} of atorvastatin and a 47% increase in the AUC (p < 0.001 for C_{max} and AUC). Clarithromycin significantly (p < 0.001) increased the AUC (and C_{max}) of all 3 statins, most markedly simvastatin (1- to 10-fold increase in AUC) and simvastatin acid (12-fold), followed by atorvastatin (greater than fourfold) and then pravastatin (almost twofold). Pravastatin has a neutral drug interaction profile relative to cytochrome P450-3A4 inhibitors, but these substrates markedly increase systemic exposure to simvastatin and atorvastatin. © 2004 by Excerpta Medica, Inc. (Am J Cardiol 2004;94:1140-1146)

A 3 is pharmacologic class, statins are exceedingly well tolerated. However, rhabdomyolysis remains a serious concern. According to postmarketing surveillance data for the United States, 91 cases of fatal rhabdomyolysis were reported per 1 million prescriptions of statins, often with cerivastatin and pravastatin, up to June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon; its incidence increases about fourfold (from ~0.3% to ~1.3%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.²⁻⁴ These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁵ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁶⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),^{13,14} protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁵ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁶⁻²¹ including over-the-counter agents and grapefruit juice.²² To delineate the potential for pharmacokinetic interactions between pravastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin when coadministered with cytochrome P450 (CYP) 3A4 inhibitors, multiple-dose studies were conducted in healthy subjects.

METHODS
Overview of study design: This report summarizes data from 4 small, short-term parallel group studies that evaluated the effects of CYP3A4 inhibitors on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of statins in a group of healthy subjects. These studies, which were conducted from January 6, 1998 through April 4, 1998, evaluated the pharmacokinetics of (1) 40 mg of pravastatin or 40 mg of simvastatin when coadministered with 480 mg of extended-release verapamil, (2) 40 mg of pravastatin or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 100 mg of nifedipine, (3) 40 mg of pravastatin or 40 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 200 mg of itraconazole, and (4) 40 mg of pravastatin, 40 mg of simvastatin, or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily. All agents were dispensed as marketed products by the investigators. The studies described in this report were conducted at the IBRD Center for Clinical Research (Neptune, New Jersey) for the verapamil, ni-

doi:10.1016/j.amjcard.2004.07.080 has been loaded

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Some drug names may already be highlighted in yellow; these have been *pre-annotated* by a computer tool.

(4) Select the claim.

4(a) First find the appropriate information in the input document: Input column *The sentence(s) that state the main assertion* specifies either a page location or a textual quotation. Find this text by going to the page location, reading through the document, or by hitting Ctrl-F and searching for the sentence.

4(b) Highlight *the sentence(s) that state the main assertion*, then click the “MP” button.

Three-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme-A reductase inhibitors (statins) are first-line treatments for hypercholesterolemia. Although exceedingly well tolerated, treatment with statins incurs a small risk of myopathy or potentially fatal rhabdomyolysis, particularly when co-administered with medications that increase their systemic exposure. Studies compared the multiple-dose pharmacokinetic interaction profiles of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin when coadministered with 4 inhibitors of cytochrome P450-3A4 isoenzymes in healthy subjects. Compared with pravastatin alone, co-administration of verapamil, mibefradil, or itraconazole with pravastatin was associated with no significant changes in pravastatin pharmacokinetics. However, concomitant verapamil increased the simvastatin area under the concentration:time curve (AUC) approximately fourfold, the maximum serum concentration (C_{max}) fivefold, and the active metabolite simvastatin acid AUC and

comparisons $p < 0.001$). Similar (greater than fourfold) important increases in these parameters and a $>60\%$ increase in the serum half-life ($p = 0.03$) of atorvastatin were observed when coadministered with mibefradil. The half-life of atorvastatin also increased by $\sim 60\%$ ($p = 0.052$) when coadministered with itraconazole, which elicited a 2.4-fold increase in the C_{max} and a 47% increase in the AUC ($p < 0.001$). Clarithromycin significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased the AUC (and C_{max}) of all 3 statins, most markedly simvastatin (~ 10 -fold increase in AUC) and simvastatin acid (12-fold), followed by atorvastatin (greater than fourfold) and then pravastatin (almost twofold). Pravastatin has a neutral drug interaction profile relative to cytochrome P450-3A4 inhibitors, but these substrates markedly increase systemic exposure to simvastatin and atorvastatin. ©2004 by Excerpta Medica, Inc.

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4(c) Next click "create a claim"

Three-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme-A reductase inhibitors (statins) are first-line treatments for hypercholesterolemia. Although exceedingly well tolerated, treatment with statins incurs a small risk of myopathy or potentially fatal rhabdomyolysis, particularly when co-administered with medications that increase their systemic exposure. Studies compared the multiple-dose pharmacokinetic interaction profiles of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin when coadministered with 4 inhibitors of cytochrome P450-3A4 isoenzymes in healthy subjects. Compared with pravastatin alone, co-administration of verapamil, mibefradil, or itraconazole with pravastatin was associated with no significant changes in pravastatin pharmacokinetics. However, concomitant verapamil increased the simvastatin area under the concentration:time curve (AUC) approximately fourfold, the maximum serum concentration (C_{max}) fivefold, and the active metabolite simvastatin acid AUC and

comparisons $p < 0.001$). Similar (greater than fourfold) important increases in these parameters and a $>60\%$ increase in the serum half-life ($p = 0.03$) of atorvastatin were observed when coadministered with mibefradil. The half-life of atorvastatin also increased by $\sim 60\%$ ($p = 0.052$) when coadministered with itraconazole, which elicited a 2.4-fold increase in the C_{max} and a 47% increase in the AUC ($p < 0.001$). Clarithromycin significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased the AUC (and C_{max}) of all 3 statins, most markedly simvastatin (~ 10 -fold increase in AUC) and simvastatin acid (12-fold), followed by atorvastatin (greater than fourfold) and then pravastatin (almost twofold). Pravastatin has a neutral drug interaction profile relative to cytochrome P450-3A4 inhibitors, but these substrates markedly increase systemic exposure to simvastatin and atorvastatin. ©2004 by Excerpta Medica, Inc.

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(5) Next we need to enter the text associated with this claim into the annotation interface.

5(a) First gather the required information from the input document, as follows:

- Drug 1. See Column "Drug"
- The property, or relationship. See Column "Property"
- Drug 2 or inhibitor. See Column "Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions)"
- The method. See Column "Study Type"
- Rejected Evidence. See Column "Meets inclusion criteria?" and Column "If you entered 'No' - explain why"

5(b) Second, select the drug name (from input column *Drug*), relationship (from input column *Property*), and method (from input column *Study Type*).

The screenshot shows a software interface for text annotation. At the top, there is a text box containing a paragraph of text. A portion of this text is highlighted in yellow: "Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution." Below the text box is an "Annotation Editor" form. The form contains the following fields: "Drug 1:" with a dropdown menu showing "Nelfinavir"; "Drug 2:" with a dropdown menu showing "Nelfinavir"; "Precipitant:" with two radio buttons, the top one being selected; "Relationship:" with a dropdown menu showing "Interact with"; and "Method:" with a dropdown menu showing "DDI clinical trial". There is also a "Rejected Evidence" checkbox which is currently unchecked. At the bottom right of the form are "Cancel" and "Save and Close" buttons. On the right side of the interface, there is a sidebar titled "Cited by other articles in PMC" listing several medical articles.

5(c) Enter the second drug (from input column "Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions)").

5(d) Indicate which drug is the precipitant by clicking the radio button labeled "Precipitant".

5(e) Input Rejected Evidence information based on input column "Meets inclusion criteria?" ("Yes" means "not reject", "No" means "reject") and column: "If you entered 'No' - explain why"(reject reason).

Pharmacokinetic assessment was performed on days 14 and 28. The study drugs were well tolerated. Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution.

Cited by other articles in PMC
Coronary artery disease risk reduction in HIV-infected persons: comparative analysis [AIDS care. 20]
Optical Isomers of Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin and Fluvastatin Enantiospecifically Activate Pregnane X Recept [PLoS ONE. 20]
Polypharmacy and Risk of Antiretroviral Drug Interactions Among the Aging HIV-Infected Population [Journal of General Internal Medicine. 20]
Risk Assessment of Mechanism-Based Inactivation in Drug-Drug

Annotation Table: Annotation Editor

Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir.

Drug1: Nelfinavir Precipitant: Relationship: interact with Method: DDI clinical trial
Drug2: simvastatin Precipitant: Relationship: Method: Rejected Evidence

Cancel Save and Close

5(f) Click “Save and Close”.

5(g) A popup appears asking what you would like to do, for this text span.

- add another claim
- add material/data for an existing claim
- finish with this span, move on

Select one of these options and click “OK”.

In this case we want to add another claim for the same text span.

This would be indicated when the SAME filename listed in input *Column: Article* has multiple rows, where those rows have the SAME text/location specified in input *Column: The sentence(s) that state the main assertion*.

Therefore, we click “add another claim from the same text span”

(6) We repeat step 5 in order to add the second claim.

Pharmacokinetic assessment was performed on days 14 and 28. The study drugs were well tolerated. Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution.

Cited by other articles in PMC
 Coronary artery disease risk reduction in HIV-infected persons: a comparative analysis [AIDS care, 2011]
 Optical Isomers of Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin and Fluvastatin Enantiospecifically Activate Pregnane X Recept [PLoS ONE, 2011]
 Polypharmacy and Risk of Antiretroviral Drug Interactions Among the Aging HIV-Infected Population [Journal of General Internal Medicine, 2011]
 Risk Assessment of Mechanism-Based Inactivation in DnaQ-Fru...

Annotation Table | Annotation Editor

Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir.

Drug1: Nelfinavir | Precipitant: | Relationship: Interact with | Method: DDI clinical trial
 Drug2: atorvastatin | Precipitant:

Rejected Evidence

Cancel | Save and Close

In this case we STILL want to add another claim for the same text span.

This would be indicated when the SAME filename listed in input *Column: Article* has multiple rows, where those rows have the SAME text/location specified in input *Column: The sentence(s) that state the main assertion*.

Therefore, we AGAIN click “add another claim”

of these two classes of drugs may cause significant drug interactions. This open-label, study was performed to determine the interactions between nelfinavir, a protease inhibitor, and a HMG CoA reductase inhibitor. Participants received either atorvastatin or simvastatin on days 14 and 28. Nelfinavir assessment was performed on days 14 and 28. The study drugs were well tolerated. Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution.

Interactions between antiretroviral drugs and therapy of the metabolic complications [Clinical Infectious Diseases, 2011]

Articles in PMC
 Coronary artery disease risk reduction in HIV-infected persons: a comparative analysis [AIDS care, 2011]
 Optical Isomers of Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin and Fluvastatin Enantiospecifically Activate Pregnane X Recept [PLoS ONE, 2011]
 Polypharmacy and Risk of Antiretroviral Drug Interactions Among the Aging HIV-Infected Population [Journal of General Internal Medicine, 2011]
 Risk Assessment of Mechanism-Based Inactivation in DnaQ-Fru...

Select next step from options:

Add data from the same text span for Claim:
 Nelfinavir_interact with_atorvastatin OK

Add another claim from the same text span OK

Move to different text span (finish) OK

(7) We again repeat step 5 for the third claim. There is a small difference because the evidence is rejected; we know this because input column *Meet Inclusion Criteria?* is “No”.

7(a) We enter Drug 1 (from input *Column Drug*), Relationship (from input *Column Property*), Method (from input *Column Study Type*) and Drug2 (from *Column “Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions)”*).

Pharmacokinetic assessment was performed on days 14 and 28. The study drugs were well tolerated. Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution.

Cited by other articles in PMC
 Coronary artery disease risk reduction in HIV-infected persons: a comparative analysis [AIDS care, 2015]
 Optical Isomers of Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin and Fluvastatin Enantiospecifically Activate Pregnane X Recept [PLoS ONE, 2015]
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 Risk Assessment of Mechanism-Based Inactivation in Drug-Drug

Annotation Table Annotation Editor

Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir.

Drug1: simvastatin Precipitant: Relationship: interact with Method: DDI clinical trial
 Drug2: Nelfinavir Precipitant:
 Rejected Evidence

Cancel Save and Close

7(b) Next we enter Rejected Evidence information based on input column “Meets inclusion criteria?” (“Yes” means “not reject”, “No” means “reject”) and column: “If you entered 'No' - explain why” (reject reason).

If reject reason doesn’t show in Reject Reason dropdown list, enter reason into comment field.

Pharmacokinetic assessment was performed on days 14 and 28. The study drugs were well tolerated. Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir. It is recommended that coadministration of simvastatin with nelfinavir should be avoided, whereas atorvastatin should be used with nelfinavir with caution.

Cited by other articles in PMC
 Coronary artery disease risk reduction in HIV-infected persons: a comparative analysis [AIDS care, 2015]
 Optical Isomers of Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin and Fluvastatin Enantiospecifically Activate Pregnane X Recept [PLoS ONE, 2015]
 Polypharmacy and Risk of Antiretroviral Drug Interactions Among the Aging HIV-Infected Population [Journal of General Internal Me...]
 Risk Assessment of Mechanism-Based Inactivation in Drug-Drug

Annotation Table Annotation Editor

Nelfinavir increased the steady-state area under the plasma concentration-time curve during one dosing period (AUC₀₋₂₄) of atorvastatin 74% and the maximum concentration (C_{max}) of atorvastatin 122% and increased the AUC₀₋₂₄ of simvastatin 505% and the C_{max} of simvastatin 517%. Neither atorvastatin nor simvastatin appeared to alter the pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir.

Drug1: simvastatin Precipitant: Relationship: interact with Method: DDI clinical trial
 Drug2: Nelfinavir Precipitant:
 Rejected Evidence Reject Reason: UNK Comment: The study is not d

Cancel Save and Close

(8) Now we start to create a claim with “substrate of” relationship from another article.

8(a) First, we need to select the claim (see also step 4).

8(b) Enter Drug 1 (from input *Column Drug*) and Relationship (from input *Column Property*).

8(c) Next we add Method (from input *Column Study Type*).

8(d) Once we choose “substrate of” for the relationship, we are prompted for the Enzyme. Enter enzyme (from input column “Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions)”) and Rejected Evidence information (from column “Meets inclusion criteria?” and column “If you entered ‘No’ - explain why”).

8(e) Once all claims are entered, click “Move to different text span (finish)”.

9) We continue to create a claim which method is Statement from another article. (For instance, the value of Column *Study Type* is “Statement” and column *Property* is “is_not_substrate_of”)

9(a) First, we need to select the claim (see also step 4).

9(b) Enter Drug 1 (from input *Column Drug*) and Relationship (from input *Column Property*).

9(c) Next we add Method (from input *Column Study Type*).

9(d) Input Enzyme (from Column Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions)) and negation (from Column Property).

9(e) Finish and click “Save and Close”.

(10) This takes you to the “Annotator Table”. This specifies the information that is desired. You will annotate a span of the document and add text, for whatever information is available in the document.

dramatically (14, 12). However, with the long-term administration of these agents, metabolic changes such as hyperglycemia (2, 8), hyperlipidemia (M. J. Jimenez-Exposito, A. Paul, A Laville, and L. Masana, Abstr. 6th Eur. Conf. Clin. Aspect Treatment HIV Infect., 1997; package insert for Sustiva [efavirenz]), and lipodystrophy (13, 21) have been observed in HIV-positive patients. The etiology of these changes is poorly understood. However, medications are prescribed to treat these metabolic changes because of concerns about the long-term cardiovascular risks. Lipid-lowering agents, especially HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors (15), are being used to reduce cholesterol and triglycerides in HIV-positive patients.

Many HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors are metabolized by the liver cytochrome CYP3A4 enzyme. Coadministration of HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors with CYP3A4 inhibitors/substrates such as

Links
 Compound
 MedGen
 PubMed
 Substance

Recent Activity

Annotation Table

Claim		Material/Data								
Nelfinavir_interact with_simvastati		Ev	No. of	Nelfinavir	simvastatin	AUC	Cmax	Clearance	Half-life	Study
Method: DDI clinical trial		Relationship	Participants	Dose	(precipitant) Dose	ratio	ratio	ratio	ratio	type
Edit Claim	View Claim									

10(a) The color of text in table stands for the value of Rejected Evidence. (Green means not rejected. Red means rejected)

10(b) The claims with different method (DDI Clinical Trial, Phenotype Clinical Study, Case Report) will have some different columns in "Annotation Table". The Claim with "Statement" method doesn't have Material/Data.

DDI Clinical Trial:

Claim		Material/Data								
Nelfinavir_interact with_simvastati		Ev	No. of	Nelfinavir	simvastatin	AUC	Cmax	Clearance	Half-life	Study
Method: DDI clinical trial		Relationship	Participants	Dose	(precipitant) Dose	ratio	ratio	ratio	ratio	type
Edit Claim	View Claim									

Phenotype Clinical Study:

Claim		Material/Data								
rosuvastatin_substrate_of_cyp2a6		Ev	No. of	rosuvastatin	Phenotype	AUC	Cmax	Clearance	Half-life	Study
Method: Phenotype clinical study		Relationship	Participants	Dose		ratio	ratio	ratio	ratio	type
Edit Claim	View Claim									

Case Report:

Claim	Material/Data																												
cholesterol_interact with_triglyceri Method: Case Report Edit Claim View Claim	add new data & material <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Reviewer</th> <th>cholesterol Dose</th> <th>triglycerides Dose</th> <th>Q1</th> <th>Q2</th> <th>Q3</th> <th>Q4</th> <th>Q5</th> <th>Q6</th> <th>Q7</th> <th>Q8</th> <th>Q9</th> <th>Q10</th> <th>Total</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>X</td> <td>NA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Reviewer	cholesterol Dose	triglycerides Dose	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	NA
Reviewer	cholesterol Dose	triglycerides Dose	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Total																
			X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	NA																

Statement:

Claim	Material/Data
concentration_interact with_simva Method: statement Edit Claim View Claim	Negate this claim Yes

Note that the claim shown is the last claim entered. But you can work on the claims in any order.

Note: if you click on a data cell without having a text span highlighted, you will get the message "please select a span before you add any materials/data".

Three-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme-A reductase inhibitors (statins) are first-line treatments for hypercholesterolemia. Although exceedingly well tolerated, treatment with statins incurs a small risk of myopathy or potentially fatal rhabdomyolysis, particularly when co-administered with medications that increase their systemic exposure. Studies compared the multiple-dose pharmacokinetic interaction profiles of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin when coadministered with 4 inhibitors of cytochrome P450-3A4 isoenzymes in healthy subjects. Compared with pravastatin alone, co-administration of verapamil, mibefradil, or itraconazole with pravastatin was associated with no significant changes in pravastatin pharmacokinetics. However, concomitant verapamil in

comparisons $p < 0.001$). Similar (greater than fourfold) important increases in these parameters and a $> 60\%$ increase in the serum half-life ($p = 0.03$) of atorvastatin were observed when coadministered with mibefradil. The half-life of atorvastatin also increased by $\sim 60\%$ ($p = 0.052$) when coadministered with itraconazole, which elicited a 2.4-fold increase in the C_{max} of atorvastatin and a 47% increase in the AUC ($p < 0.001$ for C_{max} and AUC). Clarithromycin significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased the AUC (and C_{max}) of all 3 statins, most markedly simvastatin (~ 10 -fold increase in AUC) and simvastatin acid (12-fold), followed by atorvastatin (greater than fourfold) and then pravastatin (almost twofold). Prava-

under the concentration:ti

profile relative to these substrates o simvastatin and edica, Inc.

new row for material/data

Half-life	Randomization

Annnotator Editor

Claim

simvastatin substrate of cyp3a4

Method: clinical trial

edit claim view claim

Please select a span before you add any material/data!

(11) Now we are ready to add the information associated with one claim, in the "material/data" part of the table.

11(a) First, determine which claim (row of the input document) you will work on.

11(b) Next, gather the required information from the input document, as follows:

- a. Dosage/administration information for drugs specified in the claim above. Typically, Skim near the methods [*Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the methods*]
- b. Relationship – *Column: Property*
- c. Method type – *Column: Study Type*
- d. Drug2/inhibitor – *Column: Value (drop down - for non-quantitative assertions*
- e. Participants – *Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the methods* and *Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the results*
- f. AUC Ratio, Cmax Ratio, Clearance Ratio, and/or Half-life (T1/2) Ratio – *Column: The sentence(s), table(s), and/or figure(s) that specify the results*
- g. Ev_relationship (evidence relationship) – *Column: This is evidence. If it's an "against", then selects "refuse", otherwise selects "support".*

11(c) Select the text span associated with a data item and click the MP button. Here we select the text associated with the object drug dosage and administration. Read through, select clinical trial for methods.

11(d) Roll over "add material/data for", and choose the claim you would like to add data for.

June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon; its incidence increases about fivefold (from ~0.3% to ~1.5%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.^{2,3} These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁴ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁵⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),¹³⁻¹⁶ protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁷ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁸⁻²¹ including over-the-counter agents

From the Office of Health Promotion and Disease Prevention, Department of Medicine, Emory University School of Medicine, Atlanta, Georgia. This study was supported by Bristol-Myers Squibb Co., Princeton, New Jersey; Amgen, Inc., Thousand Oaks, CA; and

METHODS

Overview of study designs: This report summarizes data from 4 small, short-term parallel-group studies that evaluated the effects of CYP3A4 inhibitors on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of statins in 4 groups of healthy subjects. These studies, which were conducted from January 6, 1998 through April 4, 1998, evaluated the pharmacokinetics of (1) 40 mg of pravastatin or 40 mg of simvastatin when coadministered with 480 mg of extended-release verapamil; (2) 40 mg of pravastatin or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 100 mg of mibefradil; (3) 40 mg of pravastatin or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 200 mg of itraconazole; and (4) 40 mg of pravastatin, 40 mg of simvastatin, or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily.

create a claim
add material/data for

clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin
clarithromycin interacts with pravastatin
simvastatin substrate of cyp3a4
simvastatin-acid substrate of cyp3a4

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11(f) The annotator table appears, and the highlighted text has been selected. The highlighted text will get associated with the data cell you click, for the claim and method shown on the left.

June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon; its incidence increases about fivefold (from ~0.3% to ~1.5%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.^{2,3} These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁴ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁵⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),¹³⁻¹⁶ protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁷ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁸⁻²¹ including over-the-counter agents

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Comment [Office1]: The actual material/data form may look a little bit different. Randomization is named as Study Design.

Annotator Editor		Annotator Table		Material / Data							
Claim											
clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin				add new row for material/data							
Method	clinical trial	Ev-Relationship	Participants	Atorvastatin Dose	Clarithromycin Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Cmax Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization	
edit claim	view claim span										

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11(g) Now click on any cell in the data table associated the highlighted text. In this case we first click on the cell labeled "Atorvastatin Dose".

11(h) Enter the dose as text (in mg). Choose the formulation from the drop down. In this case the duration (days) is not specified in the text, so we leave it blank. Choose the regimen from the drop down.

Note: For each material/data form, all the fields have to be filled out! Otherwise, the data won't be saved.

June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon; its incidence increases about fivefold (from ~0.3% to ~1.5%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.^{2,3} These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁴ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁵⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),¹³⁻¹⁶ protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁷ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁸⁻²⁴ including over-the-counter agents

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From the Office of Health Promotion and Disease Prevention, Department of Medicine, Emory University School of Medicine, Atlanta, Georgia. This study was supported by Bristol-Myers Squibb Co. Emory and Bristol-Myers Squibb are equal partners in this work.

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NOTE: Formulation

If the highlighted text does not specifically indicate that it's an oral dose (such as tablet, pill, etc), assume that the authors mean oral and select oral. If the authors specifically refer to an IV or the dose as mg/mL over time, then select IV.

11(i) Click "save". This allows you to add additional information associated with the same highlighted text span and the same claim. 10(a) In this case, the highlighted text span is also associated with the precipitant dose, so we next click "precipitant dose".

11(j) Fill in the precipitant dose (the top right corner shows the drugs, in case we need to know which drug the precipitant is). Choose the formulation from the drop down. Choose the regimen from the drop down. In this case the duration (days) is not specified in the text, so we leave it blank.

June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon; its incidence increases about fivefold (from ~0.3% to ~1.5%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.^{2,3} These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁴ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁵⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),¹³⁻¹⁶ protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁷ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁸⁻²¹ including over-the-counter agents

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From the Office of Health Promotion and Disease Prevention, Department of Medicine, Emory University School of Medicine, Atlanta, Georgia. This study was supported by Bristol-Myers Squibb Co., Princeton, New Jersey. Manuscript received February 9, 2014; accepted

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NOTE: Formulation

If the highlighted text does not specifically indicate that it's an oral dose (such as tablet, pill, etc), assume that the authors mean oral and select oral. If the authors specifically refer to an IV or the dose as mg/mL over time, then select IV.

11(k) Click "save and close".

11(l) You then get back to table view.

June 2001.¹ Statin-associated myopathy is a dose-related phenomenon: its incidence increases about fivefold (from ~0.3% to ~1.5%) when certain statins (e.g., lovastatin, simvastatin, or atorvastatin) are coadministered with medications that share their metabolic pathways and/or increase their systemic exposure.^{2,3} These include lipid-lowering agents such as fibrates⁴ (especially gemfibrozil), calcium channel blockers,⁵⁻⁸ immunosuppressive agents (e.g., cyclosporine),^{9,10} macrolide antibiotics (e.g., clarithromycin),^{11,12} imidazole antifungal agents (e.g., itraconazole),¹³⁻¹⁶ protease inhibitors for human immunodeficiency virus,¹⁷ and combinations of these and other drugs,¹⁸⁻²¹ including over-the-counter agents

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Overview of study designs: This report summarizes data from 4 small, short-term parallel-group studies that evaluated the effects of CYP3A4 inhibitors on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of statins in 4 groups of healthy subjects. These studies, which were conducted from January 6, 1998 through April 4, 1998, evaluated the pharmacokinetics of (1) 40 mg of pravastatin or 40 mg of simvastatin when coadministered with 480 mg of extended-release verapamil; (2) 40 mg of pravastatin or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 100 mg of mibefradil; (3) 40 mg of pravastatin or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 200 mg of itraconazole; and (4) 40 mg of pravastatin, 40 mg of simvastatin, or 80 mg of atorvastatin when coadministered with 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily.

From the Office of Health Promotion and Disease Prevention, Department of Medicine, Emory University School of Medicine, Atlanta, Georgia. This study was supported by Bristol-Myers Squibb Co. (NIA 148)

Annotator Editor		Annotator Table		Material / Data						
clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin				+ add new row for material/data						
Method	clinical trial	Ev-Relationship	Participants	Abundance/Dose	Clearance/Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Over Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization
edit claim	view claim span			40	50					

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12(a) Next we select the text associated with the participants.

Pharmacokinetic effects of clarithromycin on pravastatin, atorvastatin, and simvastatin
 This randomized, open-label, parallel-group study evaluated the effects of co
 clarithromycin on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of pravastatin, simvast
 atorvastatin. Forty-five healthy men and women were randomly assigned to open-label
 administration of 40 mg of pravastatin (n = 15), 40 mg of simvastatin (n = 15), or 80 mg of
 atorvastatin (n = 15). In each group, the statin was administered once daily after
 breakfast on study days 1 to 7 and days 10 to 17. All subjects also received 500 mg of
 clarithromycin twice daily (morning and evening) on days 10 to 18. Blood samples for
 pharmacokinetic analysis were obtained on days 7 and 17.

12(b) Click MP.11 (c) Roll over “add material/data for”, and choose the claim you would like to add data for.

Pharmacokinetic effects of clarithromycin on pravastatin, atorvastatin, and simvastatin

This randomized, open-label, parallel-group study evaluated the effects of clarithromycin on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin. Forty-five healthy men and women were randomly assigned to open-label administration of 40 mg of pravastatin (n = 15), 40 mg of simvastatin (n = 15), or 80 mg of atorvastatin (n = 15). In each group, the statin was administered once daily after breakfast on study days 1 to 7 and days 10 to 17. All subjects also received 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily (morning and evening) on days 10 to 18. Blood samples for pharmacokinetic analysis were obtained on days 7 and 17.

create a claim
add material/data for

- clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin
- clarithromycin interacts with pravastatin
- simvastatin substrate of cy3a4
- simvastatin-acid substrate of cy3a4

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- 12(d) Click the participants cell in table view.
- 12(e) Fill in the number of study participants.

Pharmacokinetic effects of clarithromycin on pravastatin, atorvastatin, and simvastatin

This randomized, open-label, parallel-group study evaluated the effects of concomitant clarithromycin on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin. Forty-five healthy men and women were randomly assigned to open-label administration of 40 mg of pravastatin (n = 15), 40 mg of simvastatin (n = 15), or 80 mg of atorvastatin (n = 15). In each group, the statin was administered once daily after breakfast on study days 1 to 7 and days 10 to 17. All subjects also received 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily (morning and evening) on days 10 to 18. Blood samples for pharmacokinetic analysis were obtained on days 7 and 17.

Annotator Editor Annotator Table

Material / Data clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin

Ev_relationship **Participants** Object Dose Precipitant Dose AUC Clearance Cmax Half-life Randomization

The number of study participants

cancel delete save save and close

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12(f) Click “save and close” to be taken back to the annotator table.

Pharmacokinetic effects of clarithromycin on pravastatin, atorvastatin, and simvastatin

This randomized, open-label, parallel-group study evaluated the effects of concomitant clarithromycin on the multiple-dose pharmacokinetics of pravastatin, simvastatin, and atorvastatin. Forty-five healthy men and women were randomly assigned to open-label administration of 40 mg of pravastatin (n = 15), 40 mg of simvastatin (n = 15), or 80 mg of atorvastatin (n = 15). In each group, the statin was administered once daily after breakfast on study days 1 to 7 and days 10 to 17. All subjects also received 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily (morning and evening) on days 10 to 18. Blood samples for pharmacokinetic analysis were obtained on days 7 and 17.

Annotator Editor		Annotator Table									
Claim		Material / Data									
clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin		+ odd new row for material/data									
Method	clinical trial	Ev-Relationship	Participants	Atorvastatin Dose	Clarithromycin Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Cmax Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization	
edit claim	view claim span	1		80	500						

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(13) Next we will work on the AUC Ratio.

NOTE: AUC

AUC is a measurement of the total drug exposure over time. *The focus is on the altered AUC values.* An increase in AUC means an increase in drug exposure; a decrease means a decrease in drug exposure. If the statement includes information about the AUC (which will always refer to the object drug), in the AUC Ratio fields, type the AUC Ratio value in the AUC Ratio: text box, the AUC Ratio type (percent, fold, unk), and direction (increase, decrease, unk). If the AUC Ratio is not mentioned at all, select or type unk in all fields. Sometimes, statements will refer only to exposure, not AUC Ratio directly. In those cases, assume they mean AUC Ratio, and annotate accordingly.

Examples of AUC information include:

- “Cyclosporine AUC and Cmax were determined before and after the administration of fluconazole 200 mg daily for 14 days in eight renal transplant patients who had been on cyclosporine therapy for at least 6 months and on a stable cyclosporine dose for at least 6 weeks.”
- “Concomitant treatment with rabeprazole (20 mg daily) and ketoconazole in healthy subjects decreased the bioavailability of ketoconazole by 30% and increased the AUC and Cmax for digoxin by 19% and 29%, respectively. Therefore, patients may need to be monitored when such drugs are taken concomitantly with rabeprazole. Co-administration of rabeprazole and antacids produced no clinically relevant changes in plasma rabeprazole concentrations.”

13(a) Highlight the “AUC Ratio” information.

NOTE: Please highlight the table caption instead of the data in table cell. For instance, please highlight “TABLE 4. Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin” in this case.

13(b) Click MP

13(c) Roll over “add material/data for”, and choose the claim you would like to add data for.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

Statin	Parameter	Statin Alone	Statin + Clarithromycin	%Change	p Value
Pravastatin, 40 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	18	41	+128	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	54	114	+110	<0.001
Simvastatin, 40 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	7	50	+609	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	22	219	+885	<0.001
Simvastatin acid	C _{max} (ng/ml)	1	10	+677	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	6	73	+1,092	<0.001
Atorvastatin, 80 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	21	113	+446	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	102	454	+343	<0.001

Data are geometric means.

Annotations:
 - create a claim
 - add material/data for
 - clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin
 - clarithromycin interacts with pravastatin
 - simvastatin substrate of cyp3a4
 - simvastatin-acid substrate of cyp3a4

Text on right: ...in suggest... pravasta-...ceptible to... ions with... CYP3A4 inhibitors. Although rare, rhabdomyolysis with statins remains an important and timely issue. Recently, the manufacturer of rosuvastatin wrote to United Kingdom and European prescribers to remind them that the starting dose of rosuvastatin should be 10 mg. Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, warfarin, and gemfibrozil but not with fenofibrate, azole antifungals, or

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13(d) Click the “AUC Ratio” cell in the annotation table.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

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	AUC (ng/ml/h)	102	454	+343	<0.001

Data are geometric means.

simvastatin, and atorvastatin suggest that the non-CYP substrate pravastatin is the statin least susceptible to pharmacokinetic interactions with CYP3A4 inhibitors. Although rare, rhabdomyolysis with statins remains an important and timely issue. Recently, the manufacturer of rosuvastatin wrote to United Kingdom and European prescribers to remind them that the starting dose of rosuvastatin should be 10 mg. Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, warfarin, and gemfibrozil but not with fenofibrate, azole antifungals, or

Annotation Table:

Claim		Material / Data								
clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin		Ev-Relationship	Participants	Atorvastatin Dose	Clarithromycin Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Cmax Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization
edit claim	view claim span	1	45	80	500					

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13(e) Here we type in the numerical portion of the “% Change” (343) into “AUC Ratio”, select the radio button “percent” and the AUC Ratio direction “increase”.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

Statin	Parameter	Statin Alone	Statin + Clarithromycin	%Change	p Value
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	AUC (ng/ml/h)	102	454	+343	<0.001

Data are geometric means.

simvastatin, and atorvastatin suggest that the non-CYP substrate pravastatin is the statin least susceptible to pharmacokinetic interactions with CYP3A4 inhibitors. Although rare, rhabdomyolysis with statins remains an important and timely issue. Recently, the manufacturer of rosuvastatin wrote to United Kingdom and European prescribers to remind them that the starting dose of rosuvastatin should be 10 mg.

Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, warfarin, and gemfibrozil but not with fenofibrate, azole antifungals, or

Material / Data

clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin

Ev_relationship Participants Object Dose Precipitant Dose **AUC** Clearance Cmax Half-life Randomization

AUC Ratio unchanged AUC Type unk percent fold AUC Direction unk Increase decrease

cancel delete save save and close

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13(f) When we click “save and close” the AUC Ratio appears in the table.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

Statin	Parameter	Statin Alone	Statin + Clarithromycin	%Change	p Value
Pravastatin, 40 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	18	41	+128	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	54	114	+110	<0.001
Simvastatin, 40 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	7	50	+609	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	22	219	+885	<0.001
Simvastatin acid	C _{max} (ng/ml)	1	10	+677	<0.001
	AUC (ng/ml/h)	6	73	+1,092	<0.001
Atorvastatin, 80 mg	C _{max} (ng/ml)	21	113	+446	<0.001
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Claim

Material / Data

clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin

add new row for material/data

Method	clinical trial	Participants	Num who Complete	Atorvastatin Dose	Clarithromycin Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Cmax Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization
edit claim	view claim span	1	45	80	500	343				

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(14) Next we work on the Cmax Ratio.

NOTE: Cmax is a measurement of the highest serum concentration of the drug in the blood after administration of one dose. **The focus is on the altered Cmax values.** If the statement includes information about Cmax Ratio (which will always refer to the object drug), in the Cmax Ratio fields capture the Cmax Ratio value, the Cmax Ratio type (percent, fold, unk), and Cmax Ratio direction (increase, decrease, unk) or else type/select unk in all fields accordingly.

Examples of Cmax information include:

- “Concomitant treatment with rabeprazole (20 mg daily) and ketoconazole in healthy subjects decreased the bioavailability of ketoconazole by 30% and increased the AUC and Cmax for digoxin by 19% and 29%, respectively. Therefore, patients may need to be monitored when such drugs are taken concomitantly with rabeprazole. Co-administration of rabeprazole and antacids produced no clinically relevant changes in plasma rabeprazole concentrations.”
- “There was an increase in mean repaglinide Cmax and AUC (1.7- and 2.4-fold, respectively), following repeated doses of teriflunomide and a single dose of 0.25 mg repaglinide, suggesting that teriflunomide is an inhibitor of CYP2C8 in vivo. The magnitude of interaction could be higher at the recommended repaglinide dose [see DRUG INTERACTIONS (7)].”

14(a) Next highlight the “Cmax Ratio” information.

NOTE: Please highlight the table caption instead of the data in table cell. For instance, please highlight “TABLE 4. Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin” in this case.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

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Data are geometric means.

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Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, warfarin, and gemfibrozil but not with fenofibrate, azole antifungals, or

14(b) Click MP

14(c) Roll over “add material/data for”, and choose the claim you would like to add data for.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

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Data are geometric means.

create a claim
add material/data for

clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin
clarithromycin interacts with pravastatin
simvastatin substrate of cy3a4
simvastatin-acid substrate of cy3a4

in suggest
pravasta-
ceptible to
ions with
CYP3A4 inhibitors. Although rare, rhabdomyolysis with statins remains an important and timely issue. Recently, the manufacturer of rosuvastatin wrote to United Kingdom and European prescribers to remind them that the starting dose of rosuvastatin should be 10 mg.
Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, warfarin, and gemfibrozil but not with fenofibrate, azole antifungals, or

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14(d) The table appears, select “Cmax Ratio”.

14(e) Here we use the “%Change” to specify the “Cmax Ratio”, select the radio button “percent” and the Cmax Ratio direction “increase”.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

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Data are geometric means.

that the non-CYP substrate pravastatin is the statin least susceptible to pharmacokinetic interactions with CYP3A4 inhibitors. Although rare, rhabdomyolysis with statins remains an important and timely issue. Recently, the manufacturer of rosuvastatin wrote to United Kingdom and European prescribers to remind them that the starting dose of rosuvastatin should be 10 mg.

Rosuvastatin is an inhibitor of CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 that interacts chiefly with cyclosporine, war-

Annotator Editor **Annotator Table**

Material / Data clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin

Ev_relationship Participants Object Dose Precipitant Dose AUC Clearance **Cmax** Half-life Randomization

Cmax Ratio: unchanged Cmax Type: unk percent fold Cmax Direction: unk increase decrease

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14(f) Click “save and close” to be taken back to the annotator table.

15) Verify that all the information that was available appears in the table.

TABLE 4.
Pharmacokinetic Effects of Clarithromycin on Pravastatin, Simvastatin, and Atorvastatin

Statin	Parameter	Statin Alone	Statin + Clarithromycin	%Change	p Value
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Annotator Editor **Annotator Table**

Claim **Material / Data**

clarithromycin interacts with atorvastatin

Method	Participants	Num who Complete	Atorvastatin Dose	Clarithromycin Dose(P)	AUC Ratio	Clearance Ratio	Cmax Ratio	Half-life Ratio	Randomization
edit claim	45		80	500			446		

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16) Repeat the same process (from steps 13 to 14) for Clearance ratio, half-life ratio and randomization data/material fields for the same claim.

17) When “Phenotype” column is available, repeat the same process of step 14.

First, highlight the “Phenotype” information. Then click MP and roll over “add material/data for”, and choose the claim you would like to add data for.

The table appears, select “Phenotype”. Enter Type, Metabolizer and Population information.

Treatment: Subjects were divided into two groups. The two groups were roughly matched for gender, race, and age. The treatments were as follows.

Treatment group 1. In period 1, subjects received atorvastatin calcium (Lipitor; 10 mg once a day [QD]) in the morning for the first 14 days of the study. In period 2, subjects received atorvastatin calcium (10 mg QD) plus nelfinavir (Viracept; 1,250 mg twice a day [BID]) for an additional 14 days (days 15 to 28). All atorvastatin and nelfinavir doses were taken with food.

Annotation Table Annotation Editor

Claim: atorvastatin inhibits cyp2a13

Ev relationship > Participants > Drug 1 Dose > **Phenotype** > AUC ratio > Cmax > Clearance > Half-life > study type

Healthy male or female subjects 18 to 55 years old were enrolled after the Investigation Review Board approved the study protocol and subjects signed the informed consent form. Subjects were excluded if they took medications that might affect CYP3A4 activities, took alcohol or illegal drugs or smoked during the study, or were positive for HIV, hepatitis B, or hepatitis C.

Type: Genotype Drug Phenotype Metabolizer: Poor Metabolizer Extensive Metabolizer Ultrarapid Metabolizer

Population: Asian African Caucasian Native American

Cancel Delete Save Save and Close

(18) Next we will work on entering DIPS information of Case Report.

18(a) A “DIPS Evaluation” spreadsheet will be provided for you.

Reviewer Information: First row of this spreadsheet

Question Number: *Column Question (B).*

Answer of each question: *Column Score (C and D).*

A	B	C	D	E
Author: Duell				
Question		Score	Score	
1.	Are there previous credible reports in humans? If there are case reports or prospective studies that clearly provide evidence supporting the interaction, answer YES. For case reports, at least one case should have a “possible” DIPS rating (score of 2 or higher). If a study appropriately designed to test for the interaction shows no evidence of an interaction, answer NO. If no other studies or case reports exist, answer NA (not applicable).	Yes = +1 No = -1 NA = 0	1	
2.	Is the interaction consistent with known interactive properties of the precipitant drug? Assess the mechanism of the interaction and know the properties of the precipitant drug to properly answer this question. If the interaction is consistent with known properties of the precipitant drug, answer YES. For example, there are data that support that the precipitant drug is an inhibitor of a metabolic pathway responsible for the metabolism of the object drug. Although lists of enzyme inhibitors are now common, caution is necessary when evaluating in vitro evidence of enzyme inhibition due to the potential differences in precipitant drug concentrations compared with in vivo values. If the interaction is inconsistent with known properties of the precipitant drug, answer NO. If you are unsure of the precipitant drug properties or data are insufficient to evaluate whether the interaction is consistent with the precipitant properties, answer Unk.	Yes = +1 No = -1 Unk = 0	1	
3.	Is the interaction consistent with known interactive properties of the object drug? You need to understand the pharmacokinetic and pharmacologic properties of the object drug to adequately answer this question. Pharmacokinetic properties to consider are routes of elimination, percentage of total metabolism via each elimination pathway, transporting proteins involved, extent of first-pass metabolism, genetic polymorphism that affects the disposition and pharmacodynamic response, physiological events (e.g., inflammatory responses) that affect the activities of the primary enzyme/transport protein. Pharmacologic properties to consider are receptor polymorphism and potential effects of concurrent diseases. Answering this question based on an incomplete understanding of the object drug can lead to incorrect assessment of causation. Adverse reactions occurring with drugs whose pharmacodynamic responses are affected by many factors (eg, warfarin) are more likely to be mislabeled as interactions. If the potential interaction is not consistent with known properties of the object drug, answer the question NO. If unsure of the object drug properties or data are insufficient to evaluate whether the interaction is consistent with the object drug properties and known possible effects of the precipitant drug, answer Unk or NA. The case evaluator must know the properties of the object drug to properly answer this question.	Yes = +1 No = -1 Unk/NA = 0	1	
4.	Is the event consistent with the known or reasonable time course of the interaction (onset and/or offset)? The time course of drug interactions is usually quite predictable. The half-life of the precipitant drug will provide an estimate of the length of time for maximum inhibition to occur, and the inhibited half-life of the object drug will indicate when the maximum change in object drug concentration can be expected. If the time to the onset of the interaction does not fit with the properties of the drugs, one should look for an alternative reason for the interaction. If the interaction time course is inconsistent with what would be expected, answer NO. If unable to estimate expected time course or insufficient data are available to assess the time course, answer Unk or NA.	Yes = +1 No = -1 Unk/NA = 0	1	

18(b) First, fill the “reviewer” information.

to increase the concentration of simvastatin and atorvastatin (C. Fichtenbaum, J. Gerber, S. Rosenkranz et al., Abstr. 7th Conf. Retrovir. Opportunistic Infect., abstr LB 6, 2000). Nelfinavir, like the other protease inhibitors, is an inhibitor of CYP3A4, although it is not as strong a CYP3A4 inhibitor as ritonavir. Nelfinavir is a widely prescribed protease inhibitor. It is therefore important to study the interaction of nelfinavir and HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors. Two HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors were chosen for this study. Atorvastatin was studied because it is the most prescribed HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor, and simvastatin was studied because it is particularly susceptible to CYP3A4 inhibition.

Annotation Editor
 Claim: cholesterol interact with triglycerides
 Reviewer → Drug 1 Dose → Drug 2 Dose → Q1 → Q2 → Q3 → Q4 → Q5 → Q6 → Q7 → Q8 → Q9 → Q10
 Reviewer: Author External Date: 12/22/2016 (Format: 'mm/yyyy' or 'dd/mm/yyyy')
 question scores not provided:
 Cancel Delete Save Save and Close

18(c) Repeat the same process (step 11) for Drug 1 Dose and Drug 2 Dose fields.

18(d) Check “question score not provided” only when the DIPS score is not available. If “question scores not provided” is checked, all question score input will be disabled.

18(e) If DIPS score is available, please enter the answer of each question based on spreadsheet.

For instance, the answer of this question is “No”.

(Because the point of “Yes” in this question is +1, point of “No” is -1, point of “NA” is 0. And the score of this question is -1.)

Question	Score	Score
1. Are there previous credible reports in humans? If there are case reports or prospective studies that clearly provide evidence supporting the interaction, answer YES. For case reports, at least one case should have a “possible” DIPS rating (score of 2 or higher). If a study appropriately designed to test for the interaction shows no evidence of an interaction, answer NO. If no other studies or case reports exist, answer NA (not applicable).	Yes = +1 No = -1 NA = 0	-1

inhibitors of CYP3A4. The dual protease inhibitor combination of saquinavir plus ritonavir has been shown to increase the concentration of simvastatin and atorvastatin (C. Fichtenbaum, J. Gerber, S. Rosenkranz et al., Abstr. 7th Conf. Retrovir. Opportunistic Infect., abstr LB 6, 2000). Nelfinavir, like the other protease inhibitors, is an inhibitor of CYP3A4, although it is not as strong a CYP3A4 inhibitor as ritonavir. Nelfinavir is a widely prescribed protease inhibitor. It is therefore important to study the interaction of nelfinavir and HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors. Two HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors were chosen for this study. Atorvastatin was studied because it is the most prescribed HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor, and simvastatin was studied because it is particularly susceptible to CYP3A4 inhibition.

Annotation Editor
 Claim: cholesterol interact with triglycerides
 Reviewer → Drug 1 Dose → Drug 2 Dose → Q1 → Q2 → Q3 → Q4 → Q5 → Q6 → Q7 → Q8 → Q9 → Q10
 Q1. Are there previous credible reports in humans? Hint
 Yes No NA
 Cancel Delete Save Save and Close

18(f) Click “Save” or “Save and Close” after you finish the input.

(19) Repeat the same process (from steps 8 to 18) for each of the remaining claims associated with this paper. Each claim is associated with a row of the input file.

(20) If you do as above, the annotations will be saved in the system safely. Please remember to log off NoMachine and Pulse Secure every time you finish the work.

Version History

S.No	Date	Version	Changes Description
1	10-Feb-16	V1	Creation
2	26-May-16	V2	Add authors, fix spelling of Pittsburgh, add mockups of new annotation interface. Finalized screenshots for v2.
3	21-July-16	V3	Add evidence relationship. Finalized the material/data form.
4	09-August-16	V4	Add Vlan Information, URL. Add Ratio and remove PK.

